

Preliminary Survey of the Herpetofaunal of Begun Tehsil and Peripheral Forest Area of Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary, Rajasthan

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Abstract

An Eco-tourism / tourism activity of study area has led to changes in the ecology of the area. The key objectives of this study are to update and analyze the herpetofaunal diversity in present scenario. The standered Visual Encounter Survey method with Time Constraint was used in this study. The diversity index analysis consisted of species diversity, evenness, richness, abundance, and community similarity. 31 species of herpetofauna belonging 2 order and 15 families were recorded in Begun Tehsil and Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary. In order Anura 3 families and 7 species; in order Testudines and crocodilia 1 families 1 species each; in suborder Sauria 5 families and 9 species and sub order serpentes 5 families and 13 species were recorded. The overall herpetofauna Shannon Diversity index (H') in Begun Tehsil and Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary in selected study area was (2.96); followed by, herpetofauna species evenness (E) was (0.86) herpetofauna species richness (r) was (31). The average population size of herpetofauna population size was (13.12). This research strongly supports that habitat of Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary and Begun Tehsil suited in the Chittorgarh district of Rajasthan, is currently very supportive of the life herpetofauna and to maintain the diversity of herpetofauna we need to implement conservation activities at administrative level.

Keywords

Distribution, Diversity, Herpetofauna, Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary.

Introduction

Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary located in the Chittorgarh district of Rajasthan, the Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary is a serene and picturesque retreat spanning 288 square kilometers (111 sq mi) and was established in 1988. The sanctuary is located on the western border of the Vindhya ranges and includes the Orai and Bassi dam as part of the sanctuary. Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary lies between (25°01'30" N North Latitude and 74°05'29.99" E East Longitude). The climate of this tract is sub-tropical characterized by distinct winter, summer and monsoon season. The summers commence from middle of March and the heat becomes intense in April. Rainfall in the area is very irregular and unevenly distributed. Rain generally start of June and continue up to September end. High intensity of rain is generally observed in the month of July. The average rainfall is 852 mm. The wide variation of temperature is observed round the year. The temperature reaches up to 46°C and minimum temperature falls at 0.20°C. Humidity in the air is generally low and rarely exceeds 20-25 percent except in the rainy season when it reaches between 60-80 percent. It is renowned as one of the most beloved wildlife sanctuaries of Rajasthan, a haven for those seeking solace in the embrace of nature. The sanctuary's diverse range of flora and fauna has transformed it into a paradise for city dwellers looking to hustle and bustle of urban life. With its rich biodiversity, the sanctuary is home to a variety of animals, including the elusive sloth bear, leopards, wild cats and hyenas.

Objective of study Present study is an approach to document the comprehensive database of herpetofaunal diversity having presence, occurrence and distribution at Begun Tehsil and Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary located in the Chittorgarh district of Rajasthan.

Review of Literature

For the assessment of herpetofaunal diversity at two study sites namely Begun (Tehsil) (urban) and nearby Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary (Forest cover) were selected to achieve the objectives. Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary, (2021) Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary is a wildlife sanctuary near Bassi in Chittorgarh district of Rajasthan, India, 5 kilometers from the Bassi Fort Palace. It covers 15,290 hectares and was established in 1988. The sanctuary

is located on the western border of the Vindhyachal Ranges and includes the Orai and Bassi dam as part of the sanctuary. Bassi was declared as wildlife sanctuary vide Government of Rajasthan Notification No. F-11/41/ Raj. /8186 dated 29.8.88 for the purpose of protection, propagation and development of wild life and its environment. Sen, (2010) and Yaseen et al., (2011).: We implemented this study from September 2021 to October 2022. Random surveys were carried out for assessment of herpetofaunal diversity of the study area. We spend 28 days in the field during day and night. Surveys were carried out both day and night to find out the activity pattern in reference of diurnal as well as nocturnal species. Surveys were conducted to classify microhabitats and distribution of herpetofaunal species according to microhabitats. There is recent record of an arboreal snake *Dendrelaphis tristis* by Daudin (1803) which also indicates that the state fauna has so far been under surveyed and needs more exploration to know the present status of reptilian diversity. Species were identified using standard diagnostic keys of Smith (1931, 1935, 1943), Dutta (1997), Das (2002), Whitaker and Captain (2004), Daniels, (2002), Daniel (2005), and Frost (2008).

Main Text

Surveys include the mainly Ad-hoc search method with the adjoining of Visual Encounter survey method and Transect method. Point count method was also used for the assessment the population of the organism of interest. Present study comprised with various field method exclusively and in combination also. Mainly used methods of the searching biodiversity for the present study were listed below:

Ad-hoc Search method: In this methodology worker randomly search the desired habitats for the assessing the diversity and population status of the habitat of interest.

Visual Encounter method: A Visual encounter method (VEM) is one which field personnel walk through an area or habitat for a prescribed time period systematically searching of organisms. Time is expressed as the number of person hours of searching in each area to be compared. The (VEM) is an appropriate technique for both inventory and monitoring based studies.

Quadrat sampling: Quadrat sampling consists of laying out a series of small squares (quadrates) at randomly selected sites within a habitat and thoroughly searching those squares for organism.

Diversity Indices analysis using the Shannon Wiener, Simpson's index, and Jaccard and Sorenson index was attempted by (Hollenbeck and Ripple, 2007; Krebs, 1989 ; Bibi and Ali 2013; Lawania, *et al.* 2013) looking for distribution patterns among bird communities. Biodiversity index analysis includes species diversity, species evenness, Margalef species richness, Jackknife species richness, species abundance, and community similarity. Species diversity is an expression that connects number of species to the number of individuals, while evenness index is to identify the community evenness (Kusrini 2019).

(i). Shannon-Wiener Species Diversity Index (Magguran 1988)

$$H = -\sum pi * \ln(pi)$$

Description:

H' = species diversity index;

pi = Abundance value (ni/Ni)

(ii). Species Evenness Index (Magguran 1988)

$$E = H' / \ln S$$

Description:

E= Degree of species evenness;

S = Number of species found

(iii). Species richness index (Magguran 1988)

$$Dmg = S-1' / \ln N$$

Description:

Dmg= Margalef species richness index;

N= Number of individuals found

(iv). Jackknife species richness index (Heltse and Foster 1983)

This index is used to estimate the total richness in observation location

$$S = s + (n-1/n)(k)$$

Description:

S= Jackknife species richness index;

s= number of species found;

n= number of observation path;

k=number of species found only in one observation path.

Table 1: Diversity Index values of Herpetofaunal diversity recorded at Begun Tehsil and Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary

Diversity Index	Result of Amphibians	Result of Reptiles	Over all result of Herpetofauna
Evenness / Equitability index (E)	0.8273	0.8737	0.8621
Dominance index	0.7792	0.9206	0.9336
Dominance index approximation	0.7734	0.9163	0.9312
Species Richness (r)	7	24	31
Average population size	24.8571	9.7083	13.129
Simpson index	0.2208	0.0794	0.0664
Simpson index approximation	0.2266	0.0837	0.0688
Shannon Diversity index (H')	1.61	2.78	2.96

Table 2: Species account of herpetofauna and their distribution at Begun Tehsil and Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary:

S. No	Family	Zoological Name	Common Name	IUCN (3.1) Status
Amphibians				
1	Dicroglossidae	<i>Euphyctis cyanophlyctis</i>	Indian skittering frog (Schneider,1799)	LC
2		<i>Hoplobatrachus tigerinus</i>	Indian Bull frog (Daudin 1803)	LC (IUCN 3.1)
3		<i>Fejervarya acuminata</i>	Paddy field frog (Gravenhorst,1829)	LC
4		<i>Sphaerothera breviceps</i>	Short headed burrowing frog (Schneider,1799)	LC
5	Bufo	<i>Duttaphrynus melanostictus</i>	Common Asian toad (Schneider,1799)	LC
6		<i>Bufo (Duttaphrynus) stomaticus</i>	Marbled toad (Lutken, 1864)	LC
7	Microhylidae	<i>Uperodon systoma</i>	Marbled balloon frog (Schneider,1799)	LC
Reptiles				
8	Trionychidae	<i>Lissemys punctata</i>	Indian mud or Flap-shell turtle (Lacepede 1788)	VU (IUCN 3.1)
9	Testudinidae	<i>Geochelone elegans</i>	Indian star tortoise (Schoepff 1795)	VU (IUCN 3.1)
10	Crocodylidae	<i>Crocodylus palaustris</i>	Fresh water crocodile (Lesson 1831)	VU (IUCN 3.1)
11	Gekkonidae	<i>Hemidactylus flaviviridis</i>	Northern house gecko (Ruppell 1835)	LC
12		<i>Hemidactylus Brookii</i>	Brook's gecko (Gray 1845)	LC (IUCN 3.1)
13	Agamidae	<i>Calotes versicolor</i>	Common garden lizard (Daudin 1802))	LC (IUCN 3.1)
14		<i>Sitana ponticeriana</i>	Fan throated lizard (Cuvier 1829)	LC (IUCN 3.1)
15	Scicidae	<i>Eutropis macularia</i>	Bronzed grass skink (Blyth 1853)	LC (IUCN 3.1)
16		<i>Eutropis carinata</i>	Keeled grass skink (Schneider 1801)	LC (IUCN 3.1)
17		<i>Lygosoma punctatum</i>	Dotted garden skink (Gravenhorst 1851)	LC (IUCN 3.1)
18	Varanidae	<i>Varanus bengalensis</i>	Indian monitor lizard (Daudin 1802)	NT (IUCN 3.1)
19	Typhlopidae	<i>Ramphotyphlops braminus</i>	Brahminy worm snake(Daudin 1803)	LC (IUCN 3.1)
20	Boidae	<i>Gongylophis conicus</i>	Common sand boa (Schneider 1801)	NT (IUCN 3.1)
21		<i>Eryx johnii</i>	Red sand boa (Russell 1801)	NT (IUCN 3.1)
22		<i>Python molurus</i>	Indian rock python (Linnaeus 1758)	NT (IUCN 3.1)
23	Colubridae	<i>Ptyas mucosus</i>	Common rat snake (Linnaeus 1758)	LC (IUCN 3.1)
24		<i>Lygodon aulicus</i>	Common wolf snake (Linnaeus 1758)	LC (IUCN 3.1)
25		<i>Xenochrophis piscator</i>	Checkered keelback (Schneider 1799)	LC (IUCN 3.1)
26		<i>Boiga trigonata</i>	Common cat snake (Schneider 1802)	LC (IUCN 3.1)
27		<i>Dendrelaphis tristis</i>	Common bronze back tree snake (Daudin 1803)	LC (IUCN 3.1)
28	Elapidae	<i>Bungarus caeruleus</i>	Common Indian krait (Schneider 1801)	LC (IUCN 3.1)
29		<i>Naja naja</i>	Indian cobra (Linnaeus 1758)	LC (IUCN 3.1)
30	Viperidae	<i>Daboia russelii</i>	Russell's viper (Shaw and Nodder 1797)	NE
31		<i>Echis carinatus</i>	Saw scaled viper (Schneider 1801)	LC (IUCN 3.1)

LC; Least Concern., VU; Vulnerable ; NT., Near Threatened ; NE., Not evaluated

Fig. 1. Map and satellite image showing Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary in Rajasthan.

Result and Discussion

A total of 31 species of herpetofauna belonging 2 order and 15 families were recorded in Begun Tehsil and Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary. In order Anura 3 families and 7 species; in order Testudines and crocodilia 1 families 1 species each; in suborder Sauria 5 families and 9 species and sub order serpentes 5 families and 13 species were recorded. According to IUCN Red list categories and criteria version (3.1) out of 7 amphibian species all 7 species of amphibian recorded as (LC) Least concern whereas out of 24 reptiles species 17 species of reptiles recorded as (LC) Least concern., 2 species as (VU) vulnerable., 4 species as (NT) Near Threatened and 1 species was (NE) Not evaluated.

The overall herpetofauna Shannon Diversity index (H') in Begun Tehsil and Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary in selected study area was (2.96); followed by amphibian's diversity (1.61) and reptiles diversity was (2.78) observed, overall herpetofauna species evenness (E) was (0.86) followed by amphibian's; (0.82) and reptiles species

evenness was (0.87) and overall herpetofauna species richness (r) was (31) followed by amphibian's; (7) and reptiles species richness was (24). The average population size of amphibians was observed (24.85) followed by reptiles was (9.70) overall population size as consider herpetofauna population size was (13.12). The index of species diversity, evenness, and richness was the first data taken from Begun Tehsil and Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary in selected study area and could be used to compare other results of time series research in the future. Any kind of construction in Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary would affect the habitat. Kusrini (2009) says that species richness can increase by the increased habitat diversity.

Conclusion

The wildlife research, especially in in Begun Tehsil and Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary in selected study area is the new statistical research conducted to assess the diversity level. Although there had been significant ecology changes in the development stage, 31 herpetofauna species that consisted of 7 amphibians and 24 reptiles were found in the research location. The amphibians found were 174 individuals of 3 families. While the reptile found was 233 individual of 12 families

Suggestions for the future Study

It is suggested that government policies should be formed to protect the natural habitats of herpetofauna by spreading awareness and habitat protection along with habitat restoration. The myths about the herpetofauna especially for snakes and lizard to human removed by educate the local inhabitants and by awareness programmes.

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References

1. **"Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary Chittorgarh (2021): Timings, Entry Fee & How To Reach"** . www.holidify.com. Retrieved 19 May 2021. (<https://www.holidify.com/places/chittorgarh/bassi-wildlife-sanctuary-sightseeing-121010.html>)
2. **"Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary, Chittorgarh" (2021):** www.nativeplanet.com. Retrieved 19 May 2021. (<https://www.nativeplanet.com/chittorgarh/attractions/bassi-wildlife-sanctuary>)
3. **Bibi, F. and Z. Ali, (2013):** Measurement of diversity indices of avian communities at Taunsa Barrage Wildlife Sanctuary, Pakistan. *The journal of animal and plant Science*, 23. (2). pp. 469-474.
4. **Daniel, J. C. (2002):** *The book of Indian Reptiles and Amphibians*. Bombay Natural History Society and Oxford University Press, Mumbai. VIII pp.238
5. **Daniels, R. J. R. (2005):** *Amphibians of Peninsular India*. Indian Academy of Science and University press, Hyderabad.
6. **Das, I. (2002):** *A Photographic Guide to snakes and other Reptiles of India*. New Holland Publishers (UK) Ltd, 144 pp.
7. **Dutt, U. (2023):** Assessment And Inventory Of Herpetofaunal And Avifaunal Diversity In Urban Area Of Ajmer, Rajasthan. *Global Issues: Sustainable Development, Biodiversity and Human Interference*. Kachhawa, G. and Chouhan, B. Sakshi Pub. House Jaipur. ISBN: 978-93-84232-00-0 First Ed. Pp. 140-148
8. **Dutta, S.K. (1997):** *Amphibians of India and Srilanka (Checklist and bibliography)*. Odyssey publication House, Bhubaneshwar, Orissa, India, 342 pp.
9. **Frost, D. R. (2008):** *Amphibian species of the world: an online reference*. Version 5.2 electronic database accessible at <http://research.amnh.org/herpetology/amphibian/index.php>. American Museum of Nature History. New York, USA.
10. **Hollenbeck, J. P. and Ripple, W. J.(2007):** *Aspen and Conifer Heterogeneity Effects on Bird Diversity in the Northern Yellowstone Ecosystem*. *Western North American Naturalist*. 67(1): pp. 92-101.
11. **Krebs, C. J. (1989):** *Ecological Methodology*. Harper-Collins Publishers, New York. pp. 654.
12. **Kusrini M.D. (2009):** *Pedoman Penelitian dan Survei Amfibi di Alam*. Bogor: Fakultas Kehutanan, Institut Pertanian Bogor.
13. **Kusrini, M. D. (2019):** *Metode Survey dan Penelitian Herpetofauna*. Bogor: IPB Press.
14. **Lawaniya, N. K. ; Sharma , D. D and Sharma ,V. (2013):** Occurrence and Distribution of Avianfauna from certain wetlands of Hadauti plateau, Kota, Rajasthan. *Int. Jou. of Environmental and Animal Conservation*; Vol. 2(1). pp. 8-21.
15. **Sen. M. (2010):** *Forest, Environment and climate Change Department, Government of Rajasthan, Zonal Master Plan For Eco- Sensitive Zone of Bassi Wild Life Sanctuary*. Pp 1-46.
16. **Smith, M.A. (1931):** *The fauna of British India including Ceylon and Burma, Vol. 1 (Loricata and Testudines)*. Taylor and Francis, London. 185pp.
17. **Smith, M.A. (1935):** *The fauna of British India including Ceylon and Burma, Vol. 2 (Sauria)*. Taylor and Francis, London. 440 pp.
18. **Smith, M.A. (1943):** *The fauna of British India including Ceylon and Burma, Vol. 3 (Serpentes)*. Taylor and Francis, London. 584 pp.
19. **Whitaker, R. and Captain, A. (2004):** *Snakes of India – The Field Guide*. Draco Books. Chengalpattu, Tamil Nadu, India.

20. **Yaseen, M., Sameea, M., Koli, V.K. and Dubey, S. (2011):** *An annotated checklist of Reptilian fauna of Bassi Wild Life Sanctuary, Aravalli Hills, Northwest, India. COBRA Nat. J. Vol. V(2). Pp. 25-30.*